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Coordination Template Reactions Part II. Complexes of Macrocyclic Ligand (TAAB) Tetrabenzob_{h,f,j,u}-1,5,9,13-tetrazacyclohexadecine with Dioxouranium(II), Oxovanadium(II), Oxotitanium(II) and Oxozirconium(II) Ions

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IN a previous communication from this laboratory some complexes of the title ligand with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were reported¹. In continuation of our work on macrocyclic complexes, the synthesis and characterisation of complexes of UO_2^{II} , VO^{II} , TiO^{II} and ZrO^{II} ions with the above mentioned ligand are characterised and reported in the present communication.

Keeping in view the fact that the formation of macrocycle depends upon the nature of metal, anion as well as the resulting closed ring geometry, it is found that in the present complexes, only four molecules of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde condense together to give the tetradentate ligand, while the oxygen atoms occupy the other vacant positions of the co-ordination geometry. The anions, though otherwise coordinating in nature, are outside the coordination sphere in all the complexes, as expected.

The complexes were prepared by adding the corresponding oxo-metal acetates, sulphates or

chlorides to a refluxing solution of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde freshly prepared by standard method. The resulting solution assumed a viscous appearance after refluxing for 10 h and the complexes were separated from the solution by treatment with petroleum ether—ethanol mixture. For the preparation of thiocyanate or oxalate complexes, the same procedures as described above was used, but to the refluxing solution containing oxometal chloride calculated amount of ammonium thiocyanate or oxalate was added and the ammonium chloride so formed was removed by filtration.

The elemental analysis data show that in case of all the oxo cations, only one molecule of ligand (obtained by intramolecular condensation of four molecules of aldehyde) is coordinated. The molar conductances in nitrobenzene are in the usual range of electrolytes and thus the anions are not coordinated in any case as indicated in the formulae of the complexes given in Table I. As evident, this type of condensation results in the formation of the macrocyclic ligand TAAB which completely encircles the metal ion through its four azomethine nitrogen atoms. The metal ions on the other hand acts as template directing the steric course of the reaction in the above manner and a planar completely closed ring structures results around the metal ions. The two oxygen atoms of UO_2^{II} and one of VO^{II} , TiO^{II} and ZrO^{II} are placed at the axial positions of the octahedron or square-pyramid and thus project outside the planar macrocyclic ring.

In the infrared spectra of the complexes, the NH_2 and CO stretching frequencies are absent, and a sharp band appears at 1620 cm^{-1} due to azomethine stretch and confirms the fact that Schiff base condensation with the consequent formation of macrocycle has occurred. The negative shift in its frequency of 40 cm^{-1} or more is due to its coordination^{2,3}. The infrared spectra of all the anions exhibit characteristic non-coordinated frequencies⁴⁻⁶. The $\text{U}=\text{O}$, $\text{V}=\text{O}$, $\text{Ti}=\text{O}$ and $\text{Zr}=\text{O}$ stretching frequencies are observed around 910 ± 5 , 950 ± 10 , 1050 ± 10 and $970 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, as reported for other similar complexes, and establish the presence of oxo-ions in these complexes⁷⁻¹¹.

Except the VO^{II} ion, all the other oxo-ions are d^0 systems and thus their complexes are diamagnetic in nature. In their electronic spectra only charge transfer bands are seen. The magnetic moment of VO^{II} complexes are 1.90–1.60 B.M., which is the usual range of one unpaired electron. In the electronic spectra, three bands are expected in the range 12.00–15.00, 14.50–19.00 and 21.00–30.00 kK and though their meaningful assignment has been found to be slightly difficult, the last band which is observed in the present complexes at 22.00 kK may be due to the charge transfer transition between the d_{z^2} orbital of vanadium and 2px or 2py

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	C	H	N	
1.	[UO ₂ (C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](CH ₃ COO) ₂	Yellowish brown	31.09 (29.10)	47.02 (47.82)	3.31 (3.25)	6.86 (7.00)	0.210
2.	[UO ₂ (C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂	Dark yellow	28.31 (28.10)	46.10 (46.66)	3.05 (2.67)	10.95 (10.45)	0.526
3.	[VO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)]SO ₄ .4H ₂ O	Reddish brown	9.03 (8.70)	47.52 (47.98)	4.20 (4.41)	7.63 (7.01)	1.905
4.	[VO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Brown	8.56 (7.50)	53.62 (53.49)	4.95 (4.23)	11.65 (12.00)	1.655
5.	[TiO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)]C ₂ O ₄ .4H ₂ O	Brownish black	8.12 (7.90)	56.28 (55.97)	4.96 (4.46)	8.15 (8.80)	0.185
6.	[TiO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Black	7.92 (7.20)	54.62 (53.99)	4.80 (4.25)	12.28 (12.80)	0.299
7.	[ZrO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)]Cl ₂ .8H ₂ O	Yellowish white	12.95 (12.90)	45.20 (45.88)	4.30 (4.91)	7.16 (7.05)	0.328
8.	[ZrO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂ .8H ₂ O	Brown	12.22 (11.70)	48.35 (48.82)	5.35 (4.82)	10.28 (10.80)	0.402

orbitals of oxygen atom. The other two bands at 12.50 and 14.70 kK are assigned to be due to electron transition b_2-e^* or ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^2(E) I$ and $b_2 \rightarrow b_1$ or ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$. The spectra is thus consistent with a square pyramidal structure for the complex $1^2.1^2$.

The complexes are very stable and remain unchanged on treatment with strong acids or alkalis. No substitution is found to occur when treated with other strong ligands such as di- or tri-amines, while heating with ammonium thiocyanate or oxalate results only in the replacement of anions.

It is thus evident that the ligand is bonded very firmly to oxo metal ion while the bonding of anions is somewhat weaker and hence these undergo replacement. The structure of the complexes can be presented as

where, M = UC^{IV}, VO^{IV}, TiO^{IV}, ZrO^{IV}.

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Studies on Complexes of Rare Earths with Malonohydroxamic Acid

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MALONOHYDROXAMIC acid, HOHN.O.C. CH₂.CO.NHOH, has been used successfully for the determination of a number of metal ions by spectrophotometric, gravimetric as well as chromatographic methods^{1,2}. Rare earth chlorides have been found to react with this ligand yielding compounds of stoichiometry, Ln₂(MHA)_x.xH₂O (where, Ln=Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III}; x=2 or 3; MHA⁻²=malonohydroxamate ion). As an extension to our previous investigations concerning the influence of chelate ring sizes on the coordination number and geometry exhibited by the hydroxamic acid complexes³⁻⁶, we have